

ДИЕЛЕКТРИЧЕСКАЯ ПРОНИЦАЕМОСТЬ ТВЕРДОГО РАСТВОРА $(As_2Se_3)_{0,8} - (As_2S_3)_{0,2}$ **Гурбанов М.М.,***кандидат физико-математических наук, доцент,***Годжаев М.М.,***кандидат физико-математических наук, доцент,***Гашимова А.И.***доктор философии по физико-математическим наукам,
кафедра общей физики и методики преподавания физики,**Сумгаитский государственный университет**Сумгаит, Азербайджан*DIELECTRIC PERMEABILITY OF A SOLID SOLUTION $(As_2Se_3)_{0,8} - (As_2S_3)_{0,2}$ **Gurbanov M.,***Candidate of Physical and Mathematical Sciences,**Associate-Professor,***Gojajev M.,***Candidate of Physical and Mathematical Sciences,**Associate Professor,***Hashimova A.***PhD on of Physical and Mathematical Sciences,**Department of general physics and methods of teaching physics,**Sumgait State University**Sumgait, Republic of Azerbaijan***Аннотация**

В данной работе приводятся результаты измерений диэлектрической проницаемости твердого раствора $(As_2Se_3)_{0,8} - (As_2S_3)_{0,2}$. Приводятся табличные данные значений индуктивности, сопротивлений, электропроводности, эффективности, реактивных и комплексных сопротивлений. В работе также показана возможность определений молекулярной поляризации по экспериментальным данным диэлектрической проницаемости.

Abstract

In this study, the dielectric constant of a solid solution $(As_2Se_3)_{0,8} - (As_2S_3)_{0,2}$ was measured. Measurements were made on a high-precision E7-20 (RLC) imitation measuring device. The values of inductance, resistance, conductivity, efficiency, reactive resistance, and complex resistances are given in tabular form. The possibility of determining the molecular polarization on the basis of experimental values of dielectric constant is shown.

Ключевые слова: индуктивность, емкость, активное сопротивление, реактивное сопротивление, проводимость, диэлектрическая проницаемость, коэффициент поляризации.

Keywords: inductance, capacitance, active resistance, reactive resistance, conductivity, dielectric constant, polarization coefficient.

As_2Se_3 and As_2S_3 compounds are promising materials for the development of optical memory elements and resistance converters. In these materials, the conversion effect is mainly associated with the transition from the glass phase to the crystalline phase. Electrical conductivity and dielectric constant play a key role in the management of such inverters. These materials are also used in laser technology [1, 2].

The study of the physical properties of solid solutions obtained on the basis of these compounds is also relevant in terms of expanding the scope of practical application. In this study, the values of a number of electrical parameters of the solid solution $(As_2Se_3)_{0,8} - (As_2S_3)_{0,2}$ determined by the modern E7-20 (RLC) imitation measuring device are given in tabular form and the possibility of calculating the polarization coefficient is shown.

$(As_2Se_3)_{0,8} - (As_2S_3)_{0,2}$ solid solution was synthesized from the literature on the basis of existing methodology and X-ray analysis was performed. It was found that this solid solution is also a crystalline analogue of the As_2Se_3 compound and crystallizes in a monoclinic structure. Cage parameters $a=11,95\text{\AA}$; $b=9,63\text{\AA}$; $c=4,26\text{\AA}$; $\beta=90^\circ 28'$ was measured [3]. The samples were prepared in the form of a flat capacitor to die the electrical parameters. In this case, the thickness of the samples was $0.05 \div 0.08$ cm. Measurements were made on an E7-20 (RLC) imitation measuring device with high accuracy and sensitivity. Here, as in traditional methods, voltmeter-ammeter measurement method is used.

However, this method has many advantages. First of all, it should be noted that the measurements are made at very high speeds (25 measurements per sec-

ond). Here, at the same time, inductance (L), capacitance (C), active resistance (R), conductivity (G), efficiency (Q), reactive resistance (X) and complex resistance (Z) are determined.

Another advantage of this method is that measurements can be made in an electric field with a wide range of frequencies ($f = 20 \div 10^6 \text{ Hz}$). At the same time, the accuracy of the measurements is higher. The relative error when measuring L, C and R parameters is $\pm 0.001\%$.

The working frequency used in the measurement is transferred from the generator to the converter in the

measuring system, where it is divided into two sinusoidal voltages and converted into a form visible in numbers. The values of the measured parameters are determined by calculation and are displayed.

This measuring device also has software, and the values of all studied parameters are determined and recorded [4].

The results of measurements carried out in the electric field of different frequencies at room temperature for a solid solution $(As_2Se_3)_{0,8} - (As_2S_3)_{0,2}$ are given in the table.

Table

f, kHz	C, pF	$R, \text{M}\Omega$	$Z, \text{M}\Omega$	ϵ
0,025	2,7	9900	2400	35,64
0,5	2,4	4600	133	31,68
5	2,3	700	14	30,36
10	2,2	400	7	30,09
20	2,1	100	3,5	29,71
100	2,4	3,4	0,65	31,94
200	2,5	9,9	0,32	33,13
500	2,6	10	0,12	34,32
1000	3,1	1,6	0,05	40,65

As can be seen from the table, as the frequency of the electric field changes, both the active and complex resistances decrease, and the value of the dielectric constant, as well as the electric capacitance, remains almost unchanged. Such a change can be attributed to the molecular polarization that takes place within the substance under the influence of the field.

In order to study the possible changes in the molecular structure within a substance under the influence of an electric field, the molecular polarization based on the table values of dielectric constant of a solid solution $(As_2Se_3)_{0,8} - (As_2S_3)_{0,2}$ can be determined.

It is known that there is such a relationship between the dielectric constant (ϵ) and the polarization coefficient (β).

$$\frac{\epsilon-1}{\epsilon+2} = \frac{n\beta}{3} \dots \quad (1)$$

here - n is the number of charged ions per unit volume. Its value can be determined in this way by the molar mass (M), density (ρ) and Avagadro constant N_A of the substance.

$$n = \rho \frac{N_A}{M} \dots \quad (2)$$

From these formulas we get

$$\beta = \frac{3(\epsilon-1)M}{(\epsilon+2)\rho N_A} \dots \quad (3)$$

Thus, by finding the value of β , it is possible to draw some conclusions about the molecular changes that take place within matter on the basis of existing

theoretical models. The value of β calculated on the basis of the dielectric constant corresponding to the average frequency intervals of the field for a solid solution $(As_2Se_3)_{0,8} - (As_2S_3)_{0,2}$ was $\sim 3 \cdot 10^{-22} \text{ sm}^3$.

It should also be noted that the conversion effect in memory elements made from the studied solid solution $(As_2Se_3)_{0,8} - (As_2S_3)_{0,2}$ is due to the phase transition between the glass and the crystal structure happens. The high electrical conductivity of these materials is due to the sliding or displacement of atoms inside the crystal.

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